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ABOUT COST ACTION SAGA (CA17131)

The Soil Science and Archaeo-Geophysics Alliance is an interdisciplinary network of scientists that aims to develop, promote and facilitate scientific activities that integrates archaeo-geophysics and soil science with the overall goal of maximising interpretation of proxy data for archaeological investigations. SAGA's network and related activities are funded by the European Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST).

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EDITOR'S ADDRESS

Dr Agnese Kukela
Assistant professor, University of Latvia
COST Action SAGA Science & Communication Manager

Dear reader,

It is my pleasure to offer to your attention SAGA's third and final newsletter. As per usual, we are giving an update on the Working Groups' activities, supported Short Term Scientific Missions and Virtual Networking. Traditionally, the Chairman of our Action gives a brief introduction to the main results of SAGA and highlights some of the future plans for our network. Two members of SAGA's team from Spain and France are revealing their thoughts and experience on being a researcher that you might find interesting and exciting. In this newsletter you will also find an introduction and a brief description of SAGA's Database that is now open to the public.

For more than four years SAGA's multidisciplinary international scientific team has worked on numerous outputs of the Action, such as training schools, publications, meetings and many more. We are happy and proud to mark the end of SAGA COST Action and welcome a united network of scientists who are willing and ready to continue further cooperation.

Have a pleasant read!

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[Agnese Kukela](#), [Carmen Cuenca-Garcia](#), [Sebastiano D'Amico](#), [Philippe De Smedt](#), [Jan Horák](#), [Simo Spasov](#), [Mercedes Solla](#), [Elina Aidona](#), [Mezgeen Rasol](#), [Apostolos Sarris](#), [Krzysztof Kiersnowski](#), [Hana Grison](#) and [Radomir Ivanovic](#).

AN UPDATE FROM THE CHAIR

Dear colleagues,

Since our final meeting in Bonnie Trondheim, which my fellow LO colleagues and I thoroughly enjoyed hosting, and the official conclusion of our Action on 25 April 2023, I would like to provide you with a few updates in this final newsletter.

First and foremost, I am pleased to announce that the SAGA Database is now open for public searches and data entry upon registration (<https://www.saga-cost.eu/user-login.php>). The database includes a dedicated section on 'Equipment,' which maps the geophysical and soil analysis instrumentation available in various COST member countries, aiming to facilitate research collaborations. It also contains other sections such as 'Methods,' providing comprehensive information on soil analytical and geophysical methods, as well as associated soil factors or properties. We encourage you to explore and utilise this resource, and we also welcome your contributions to help expand its content.

We are currently in discussions with the International Society for Archaeological Prospection (ISAP) to join them. During the recent Management Committee meetings, SAGA members expressed their commitment to continue collaboration beyond the conclusion of the COST project. It was unanimously agreed that affiliating with an established association would provide the next framework for ongoing activities. After careful consideration, ISAP emerged as the optimal group to align with due to their expertise in prospection and the potential complementarity that integrating SAGA members could offer. We have had promising initial discussions, and ISAP has expressed a willingness to welcome the SAGA community. Further information will reach our members soon.

We have also established a collection in the COST Gateway on Open Research Europe, that will serve as a specialised platform for publishing upcoming SAGA-related research. This collection, accessible at <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/collections/geophysics-and-soil-science-in-archaeology/about>, will provide our community with a cost-free open access avenue to continue sharing findings, insights, and advancements in the field of geophysics and soil science in archaeological prospection, site/landscape characterisation, and monitoring.

I have recently submitted our final report to COST, and I would like to express my gratitude to all of you for your assistance in completing this last task. Allow me to highlight some accomplishments. Over the course of these four years of collaborative work, which included a six-month extension due to the pandemic, we facilitated scientific discourse aimed at exploring integrated field procedures and solutions for enhanced data interpretation in archaeo-geophysics with 10 meetings, including two scientific workshops, and 31 short-term scientific missions. We have also conducted six training events (four on-site training schools and two online tutorials/workshops). In addition to the database, our outputs include meeting and training school reports, two books of abstracts, and a total of 53 scientific publications (22 journal papers, 12 conference papers, and 19 book chapters). These publications comprise review papers that examine critical aspects such as the "noise" or "background" components within archaeo-geophysical datasets, and methodological studies offering tools for

AN UPDATE FROM THE CHAIR

data integration and parameterisation. They also include case studies that showcase the potential of integrated approaches to provide complementary archaeological information, and to assess soil contrast's properties and dynamics which are instrumental in the detection of buried archaeological features. Furthermore, we are in the process of publishing a contributed book, which serves as the first country-based retrospective on the evolution of geophysical applications in archaeological investigations within the academic and cultural heritage management sectors across 18 countries.

Despite the challenges posed by the pandemic, we managed to create a resilient hub for training and exchange of ideas that have led to the formulation of 15 research proposals and the promotion of our approaches in countries where the use of geophysical methods in archaeology was still in its early stages.

To conclude, and from a personal perspective, I bring this project to a close on a high positive note and with a deep sense of gratitude for the opportunity to have collaborated with such an exceptional group of scientists who are also outstanding individuals.

Salud

Dr Carmen Cuenca-García (Trondheim, 8th June 2023)

Group photo from the final meeting in Trondheim. Photo: Krzysztof Kiersnowski

PAST EVENTS

Training School on Magnetic Laboratory Methods in support of archaeological and archaeo-geophysical research methods
Institute of Geophysics of the Czech Academy of Sciences
Prague, 28 -31 March 2022

The aim of this Training school (TS) was to improve participant's ability to obtain, analyse and interpret magnetic data with relevance to archaeo-geophysical research methods.

The content of the TS included:

- Introduction to magnetic property characterisation focusing on soil and archaeological material (magnetic susceptibility, remanence and hysteresis characterisation etc.)
- Data analysis and interpretation session with a variety of soils from 'natural' to archaeological ones.
- Applications of Archaeomagnetic dating techniques, with reference to archaeology case studies.
- Hands-on sessions: demonstration how to perform archaeomagnetic measurements and to determine paleo-firing temperatures incl. sampling, data processing.

There were 14 participants and 6 trainers from 14 COST Action SAGA signatory countries in this TS.

Figure 1. Group photo – SAGA TS3 participants (photo by R. Klanica).

PAST EVENTS

Figure 2. Practical training of laboratory measurements in the lecture hall (photo by K. Bondar).

[Training School in ER and GPR survey with related geoarchaeological methods](#)

The Archaeological Museum of the North Macedonia

Volandovo, 10 – 17 April 2022

This TS was addressed to Master students, PhD candidates, postdoctoral researchers, field archaeologists, curators and other professionals working in cultural heritage management with none or some understanding in those techniques. The objective of this TS was to provide some fundamentals and a clear methodological understanding of routine geophysical and soil science methods used in archaeological investigations. The theoretical sessions were complemented with hands-on sessions at the archaeological sites Stakina Češma and Isar Marvinci in Valandovo and Gradište Negotino in the North Macedonia.

The main learning outcomes of this TS included:

- Understand the basis of the most-used archaeo-geophysical techniques.
- Understand the benefits of incorporating soil science & geophysics before, during & after excavation planning phase.
- Develop competencies to improve archaeological interpretation of geophysical data.
- Develop skills to apply geophysical techniques & soil analyses to improve archaeological investigations.

There were 11 trainees from the North Macedonia participating in this TS and 3 trainers from academic and industry environments. Two of the trainers Martin and Anne Roseveare were related to the company TigerGeo Ltd. from UK and MC of COST SAGA and one of the trainers, David Jordan, was related to Liverpool John Moores University.

PAST EVENTS

Figure 1. Group photo – SAGA TS4 participants (photo by R.Ivanovic).

Figure 2. Practical session on GPR prospection (photo by R.Ivanovic).

PAST EVENTS

The final meeting of COST Action SAGA took place in Trondheim on April 18-20, 2023. This last gathering was hosted by the Department of Archaeology and Cultural History, NTNU. The event combined a 2-day conference (18-19/04/23) as well as the last Management Committee meeting (20/04/23).

The Workshop topics were focusing on:

1. Integrated approaches to archaeology that combine geophysics and soil science
2. Modelling archaeological environments and geophysical responses
3. Multivariate proxy data analysis
4. Training Schools experiences and outputs
5. Presentation of new projects

The book of abstracts of the workshop is available at https://www.saga-cost.eu/meeting-abstracts.php?id_meeting=10. The winner of the award for the best poster presentation was Dr Hazel Deniz Toktay for her contribution 'Depth Determination of Potential Archaeological Structures on Total Magnetic Anomaly Maps: Oluz Mound Example(Turkey)'.

Here are the best moments captured in photos by our colleague Krzysztof Kiersnowski.

HIGHLIGHTS FROM THE WORKING GROUPS

WG1

*Knowledge
Creation,
Exchange &
Development*

-by Dr Clare Wilson

It was great to catch up with some of you in person in Sofia, here we met with WG4 and reviewed the WG1 deliverables. Whilst not all of the activities have been able to progress as originally planned, it was clear that through the ongoing hard work of SAGA members we are able to put a tick against each of our deliverables.

Activity in WG1 since the last newsletter has focused on completing the databases and Zotero bibliography. Through the hard work of Roman Pasteka and Jorg Fassbinder, we have databases now set up and embedded in the SAGA web site. Through WG1 communications and SAGATHONS we have populated the WG1 databases with information. The Zotero library of literature has also been created and aligns with the SAGA key deliverables. Thank you for the additions to this from WG1 members and at the meeting in Trondheim a SAGATHON session focused on the library means that it is now well populated. We have a little more work to do to tidy up the library and remove supuplicate entries, but this should now provide a valuable resource for SAGA members and interested external visitors.

WG2

*Integrated Field
Methods
& Testing*

-by Dr Philippe De Smedt

During the last grant period, WG2 successfully achieved its core objective of optimising field solutions for archaeological research by combining geophysical, archaeological, and soil sampling methods through specific research and dissemination activities. The efficient fulfilment of STSMs, which focused on field methods and data integration, performed by researchers such as J. Kainz, J. Verhegge, and G.M. Veirana, provided a robust basis for fine-tuning and evaluating field protocols and associated analytical procedures. Building on the success of the 2021 Virtual Workshop on current practice in monitoring and development-led archaeology (held in Ghent, BE and online), a successful session was held at EAA2022 (Budapest, HU, 09.2022), which emphasised translating research outcomes into education in archaeological prospection and their implementation in development-led archaeology. These efforts are being disseminated through the SAGA database, mainly in the method-related sections and literature overviews, as a closing point of our WG's activities. In addition, pending result publications will further enhance the dissemination of our research findings.

WG3

*Data Integration,
Visualisation &
Parameterisation*

-by Dr Jan Horák

We worked on many things in the WG3 since the time of the last newsletter. Michel Dabas, Julien Thiesson and François-Xavier Simon worked on the French chapter for SAGA book. Armin Schmidt also co-wrote an article with Michel Dabas and Apostolos Sarris. The topic was a noise in the data (title "Dreaming of Perfect Data: Characterizing Noise in Archaeo-Geophysical Measurements" in *Geosciences*). This paper was a result of Armin's STSM in Paris (host Michel Dabas). Mercedes Solla Carracelas was working on a paper related to SAGA (title "GPR applied to monumental stone conservation: application to the rock necropolis of San Vitor de Barxacova in NW Spain" in *Surveys in Geophysics*). Nikos Papadopoulos, François-Xavi-

HIGHLIGHTS FROM THE WORKING GROUPS

er Simon (host) and Kleantith Simyrdanis (grantee) were involved in STSM called: "Literature Review for Joint Inversion of geophysical data". Another STSM was performed by Richard Hewitt in Prague (host Jan Horák), followed by Jan's visit in Madrid at Richard's University. These activities were focused on application of randomisation methods while analysing geophysical data and its following usage in integration of geochemical and geophysical data. Armin Schmidt (grantee) was also involved in Virtual Mobility Grant called "Virtual Tutorials: geophysics and soil properties". In the future, we will focus on creating guidelines for the methods we are developing. We also plan some STSMs, for some of them we could need an applicant (topics of GPR, magnetic susceptibility and gradiometers).

Since Sofia meeting, we focused mainly on the publications. Some of us worked on their respective chapters in SAGA book on national states of the art of geophysical research (e.g. Julien Thiesson on France). Others focused directly on WG3 tasks: Michel Dabas prepared a report on a topic of modelling software, Jan Horák wrote an article about the data integration (cowrote by Richard Hewitt, Julien Thiesson, Martin Janovský, Roman Křivánek and Alžběta Danielisová). Another article focused on the compositional nature of GPR data was written by Jan Horák and Richard Hewitt, Julien Thiesson, Martin Janovský, Mercedes Solla and Ekhine Garcia. Both are now in various stages of publication. Both these studies are also connected to the methodologic workflow developed in WG3 and turned into the guidelines, which will be freely accessible after publication of the articles. Some of the WG3 members also co-organised a session in EAA conference in Budapest (session # 397 "Archaeological Prospection and Field Evaluation Practice from Bologna Process to Convention of La Valetta. Do We Practice What We Preach?").

WG4

*Training,
Dissemination
& Outreach*

-by Dr Sebastiano D'Amico

The WG4 aims to demonstrate the benefits of incorporating soil science and geophysics during the planning of excavations to curators, field archaeologists as well as the new generation of scientists and practitioners. It contributes to the development of specialised skills and cross-disciplinary capacity. During the lifetime of the Action, the WP4 worked closely with training school organisers in order to offer hands-on practical activities to young researchers and professionals. The WG4 also contributed to the dissemination with the development of the SAGA's website and IT infrastructure as well as the constitution of the database containing useful information about the SAGA goals and activities and available resources.

MEET OUR MEMBERS

Dr Mercedes Solla

SAGA's MC Member (Spain)

(<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Mercedes-Solla>)

Dr. Mercedes Solla is a "Ramón y Cajal" researcher at the University of Vigo (Spain). In 2010 she obtained her PhD with International Mention, Honors and Extraordinary PhD Award from the University of Vigo in the field of geodesic and geophysics. She is Core Group Member of COST Action SAGA (CA17131) "The soil science & archaeo-geophysics alliance: going beyond prospection" and elected Policy Coordinator (2018-2022). She was an active Management Committee Member of COST Action TU1208 "Civil Engineering Applications of Ground Penetrating Radar", and vice-chair of the workgroup IV (2013-2017). Her research interests include the use of GPR for subsurface prospection, the applications of GPR in civil engineering and cultural heritage, and the use of electromagnetic modelling for advanced data interpretation.

She has published 57 research papers in JCR journals (h-index 24, Scopus), and more than 130 publications on peer-refereed journals, book chapters, conference proceedings and technical reports. She is editor of 3 international books and co-author of 1 patent. She has participated as a researcher 23 competitive projects, including 5 H2020, 1 Interreg, 3 international and 13 national (being MR in 2 of them) and in 40 R&D contracts with companies and agencies (Main Researcher in 7 of them). She has supervised 6 PhD theses (1 in progress), 14 Master theses and 25 final degree projects. She is the Academic Secretary of the Interuniversity Doctoral Programme in Geotechnologies applied to Construction, Energy and Industry from the Universities of Vigo and Salamanca, and Academic Secretary of the Master's Degree in Valuation, Management and Protection of Heritage from the University of Vigo.

What inspired you to become a researcher?

Since childhood, when someone asked me what I wanted to be when I grow up, I always said - a researcher. I think this inspiration came from the cartoons and movies I used to watch, like Willy Fog and Indiana Jones. Also, I think that being the only child in the family made me develop more creativity and become independent.

When I decided to continue with the doctoral studies, I had three different proposals by previous teachers from my bachelor/master degree in Forestry Engineering; GPR, Remote Sensing (Photogrammetry / LiDAR) or forest fires. Finally, I opted for the GPR due to its versatility and applicability to numerous fields of application, together with the thrill of being able to "see" the unknown.

What is your favourite aspect of your research?

Research is a huge source of motivation to continue learning. Certainly, my dedication to research, for almost 16 years, has helped me grow as a creative and critical person. In my view, it is one of the most generous and rewarding professions. My research topic involves a relatively small scientific community, which has allowed me to establish very good relationships with other colleagues around the world, some becoming close friends.

Your most important or most surprising scientific finding?

The most surprising scientific findings are those connected to archaeological prospection. I highlight the project "*The Syrian Middle Euphrates Archaeological Project (PAMES)*", in which a GPR study was conducted to examine the urban development and architecture of an early bronze age city at Tell Qubr Abu al-'Atiq (middle of the 3rd millennium BC). The GPR imaging revealed a circular enclosure wall with several gates and a possible moat. This discovery might re-

GPR study with a 500 MHz antenna to investigate foundation settlements in an Indiana style house (Cabanas, NW Spain).

GPR study with a 2.3 GHz antenna to assess the state of conservation (detection and localisation of internal damages like fractures and voids) of the rock necropolis of San Vitor de Barxacova (Ourense, NW Spain) consisting of 56 anthropomorphic graves carved into the natural rock.

sult in reconstruction of the northern settlement of the Syrian-Mesopotamian Kingdom of Mari.

From a development perspective, my research has provided new approaches to help GPR interpretation (forward modelling and combination with other NDTs like infrared thermography and LiDAR), as well as algorithms (based on amplitude spectrum and texture analysis) to highlight and extract potential features such as thicknesses, fractures and cavities in monumental stone.

How did you become involved in our Action?

My main interest in participating in SAGA Action lies in the opportunities to collaborate with other research groups or companies, to carry out research visits (STSM) and to have more international visibility within the scientific community, while being at the forefront of the latest research and open lines in the field of geophysics for the evaluation of cultural heritage and archaeology. I had been an active member of COST Action TU1208, with a very good experience from both professional and personal points of view, so I decided to join SAGA Action.

GPR works for the documentation and preservation of the Monastery of Batalha (Leiria, Portugal).

What are your future scientific plans?

My main goal is to get a permanent position at the University of Vigo, after my "Ramón y Cajal" contract, and to establish a research group devoted to non-destructive evaluation in Transport Infrastructure and in heritage buildings/structures (including complementary geophysical methods and remote sensing (InSAR)). My current research is mainly related to automatic detection and GPR data digitisation into information models (GIS/BIM).

What you like to do when you aren't working on research?

I love hiking and landscape photography. Travelling is another of my passions, exploring different cultures. Otherwise, I love spending time with my family and friends, just having some drink or enjoying a sunny day at the beach.

Dr Mezgeen Rasol

SAGA's MC Member (France)

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Mezgeen-Rasol-2>

Mezgeen Rasol is a postdoctoral research fellow at Gustave Eiffel University and involving with in the EMGCU-MAST-IFSATTR team in Paris, France. His research work focuses on road transport Infrastructure monitoring mainly applying non-destructive techniques - Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) in particular, in field surveys and laboratory measurements. However, he is keen to validate NDT data with computational modelling, and intelligent data analysis approaches such as machine learning. He has published more than 25 publications in high quality journals and conferences.

He has been involved in various COST ACTIONS, Horizon2020 research projects and international collaborations during his research career experience. He is working on two different topics related to road transport infrastructure monitoring in the framework of the PANOPTIS and HERON Horizon2020 project. Mezgeen have been involved in various projects that link between industry and research which make him consider his career as an engineer and can involve in significant changes for a great industry research innovation.

What inspired you to become a researcher?

Nice question. In one word, I can say: PASSION! I consider myself as an engineer who is passionate about the research and emerging technology. More specifically, I enjoy critical thinking and solving problems.

What is your favourite aspect of your research?

Your questions are making me think, and it can be a good answer to your question. I enjoy thinking and finding a reliable approach to overcome a key challenge in order to provide a robust and sustainable road transport infrastructure.

MEET OUR MEMBERS

Your most important or most surprising scientific finding?

I believe in quality of work, and I support honest and responsible work. For this, I can say most of my works come as a result of great collaborations. One of the tasks that I enjoyed lately working on is non-destructive monitoring of corrosion in a prestressed concrete bridge in Paris. The work is still undergoing.

From a development perspective, my research has provided new approaches to help GPR interpretation (forward modelling and combination with other NDTs like infrared thermography and LiDAR), as well as algorithms (based on amplitude spectrum and texture analysis) to highlight and extract potential features such as thicknesses, fractures and cavities in monumental stone.

Non-destructive monitoring of prestressed concrete Bridge in Paris, September 2021.

How did you become involved in our Action?

I was aware about COST Association since several years. I have been participated in different COST Actions during my PhD. SAGA was the continuation of my previous collaborations. SAGA is a great project to connect with many great minds. During my PhD journey until now, yes, I called it a journey regardless of the workload, I enjoyed PhD and SAGA was one of the networks that supported me to expand my network and observe different aspects of research questions.

What are your future scientific plans?

I am passionate about the great link between industry and research. I would like to continue in this combination and provide supporting tools based on emerging technology and innovation approaches for road transport infrastructure monitoring and civil engineering application, in general.

What you like to do when you aren't working on research?

I love listening to Podcasts. I am a fan of landscape and nature, I enjoy discovering new things including nature life, cuisine, reading. Besides above-mentioned activities I enjoy walking, hiking and camping. Camping has a great influence on Kurdish culture as we experienced during childhood for the Nowruz anniversary, I enjoy spending camping time with my family and friends.

VISIT OUR MEMBERS PROFILE PAGE

<https://www.saga-cost.eu/list-of-participants.php>

VIRTUAL NETWORKING SUPPORT

Before the travel possibilities were restored again, two Virtual Mobility (VM) calls were announced and 3 VM events were approved from SAGA members and inclusive countries are included. The information, links, on-line application guideline, forms and templates related to the VNT and VM were embedded and announced on SAGA website and other communication channels.

During the grant period 3, 5 main virtual events are organised by different SAGA members from different EU countries. Different event formats are organised considering Database meeting among SAGA members, Exploring approaches of different database, and also virtual tutorials. The main topics of the virtual events are as followings:

1. SAGA Equipment Data Base (organiser Andrei Asăndulesei)

The meeting of progress and advances related to the SAGA Equipment Database by SAGA Database section coordinator Andrei Asandulesei. During this meeting several aspects of data managements, uploading, downloading database query and using publicly is discussed. During our first session only 11 participants representing 12 of our 38 countries attended the event.

2. Preparing and finalising different approaches for SAGA Database (organiser Martin Janovsky)

The main objective of the VMG regarding equipment section of the database was to update (data entry is checked) and make it available for the public in this grant period. Beside an online meeting with Saga members (coordinated with Andrei Asăndulesei) in order to clarify some aspects concerning the fields from the section and some others related with the functionality of the platform itself.

3. Unveiling the hidden past: A Norwegian-Finnish collaboration among the application of large-scale geophysical prospection in archaeology at Lake Lepinjärvi, south-west Finland (organiser Wesa Perttola)

The VM was organised as a five-day online workshop. The participants from Finland (Wesa Perttola, Satu Koivisto and Tarja Knuutinen) familiarised themselves with the 3D-Radar Examiner 3 software and analysed c. 5 hectares of GPR data under the instruction of Arne Anderson Stamnes and Carmen Cuenca-Garcia. The dataset was collected from Karjaa Lepinjärvi area (SW Finland) in March 2020 in the vicinity of several Early and Mid Iron Age sites and it constituted the first multichannel and the largest GPR study done in Finland on an archaeological site to date. In addition, a brief look was taken into the magnetometer data collected on the site in 2020. After final processing and reporting, all datasets will be made freely available online in the future.

4. Virtual tutorials: Geophysics and soil properties (3 events) (organiser Armin Schmidt)

Three experts from the SAGA project delivered three online tutorial events (3 Sept, 27 Sept and 4 Oct 2021) on the link between geophysical measurements and soil properties.

The attendance was from 30 different countries including from SAGA member countries, and internationally for example USA, Asia (such as India) and Middle Eastern countries.

Participants asked interesting and in-depth questions, providing considerable scope for useful discussions. They were eager to find answers and wanted to know even small details. Tutors providing references was useful for participants.

VIRTUAL NETWORKING SUPPORT

In line with the SAGA COST Action Strategy, and the Covid-19 travel restriction, and difficulties, many different measures were undertaken to allow access to the online tutorial for as many people as possible in order to continue the research exploration, collaboration, and further advance current projects and new projects in-lined with SAGA strategy and mission.

For this reason, in order to further promote, and continue an active collaboration a VM tools made it possible to reach more audience and even make it easier to have participation from different European countries and other international partners of SAGA cost action.

The tutorials/events and online workshops were available world-wide (including to NNCs and IPCs) to interested students, researchers and practitioners from academy and industry since the online format allowed convenient participation without travel and easy to access with mostly ZOOM meetings (provided by VNT coordinator and supported by Gustave Eiffel University in France). Each event was held at a different time of day to facilitate attendance for as many people as possible during their working hours.

The funding is limited to 1500 EUR per proposal (VM grant), which is allowed making attending the tutorials free of charge for all participants, which considerably lowered the threshold for participation. Another measure to encourage active participation by attendees was to not make recordings of the sessions available online, as it had become apparent from initial enquiries that some participants would have been uncomfortable having their questions visible to others.

Overall, all events were specifically tailored for inclusiveness and removing circumstantial barriers as much as possible.

Based on the positive reception of the events it should be considered to run a similar series of different tutorials, workshops, and hands-on events again, maybe next year or next grant period.

To finalise the idea of the pilot project of the VNT and VM grants is very successful and provide more easy-access, exchange knowledge, continuation of different tasks and projects for SAGA to fulfil the expected deliverables and also new training session.

SUPPORTED STSMs (2021-2023)

During these years (2021-2023) 3 calls for STSMs have been announced and 15 applications have been granted. A list of the STSM grantees is given below:

GRANT PERIOD 3

Emanuele Colica (University of Malta)

STSM title: Geophysical measurements and experimentations applied to cultural heritage

STSM start and end date:: 2021-07-04 to 2021-07-25, Host: University of Calabria

The aim of the present short term scientific mission was to identify the optimal solution for data collection using geophysical techniques and passive seismic measurements in the Salento area and finally integrate these data to a 3D model created by Structure-from-Motion photogrammetry.

In collaboration with University of Calabria, ISPC-CNR and IREA-CNR, they used ground penetrating radar and passive seismic techniques, investigating monuments and archaeological sites in the Salento area.

The performed activities integrate near and remote sensing methods, aiming particularly at quantitative data integration following the principles of task 3 – WG 2 (INTEGRATED FIELD METHODS & TESTING).

Sebastiano D'Amico (Department of Geosciences, University of Malta)

STSM title: Applied Physics and Geophysics surveys at the Gela Archaeological Site

STSM start and end date: 2021-06-27 to 2021-07-27, Host: University of Messina

The main goal of the Short Term Scientific Mission (STSM) was to acquire geophysical data (e.g. Georadar and passive seismic data, georesistivity) as well as spectroscopy data at the archaeological site of Gela (Italy). During the STSM they collected sample data as well as perform in situ analysis. The overall goal was to mainly investigate new portions of the archaeological site, to perform a detailed topographical campaign as well as to proceed with the digitalisation of the site and the creation of detailed (and scaled) 3D digital models through the use of Lidar and photogrammetric techniques. Finally, during the STSM a GIS repository was created in order to properly archive all data collected at the (e.g. geomorphological, geophysical, and spectroscopy data). During the STSM samples from the Greek archaeological remains (mainly walls of the ancient city) were collected with the aim of characterising the material and investigate the potential provenance and try to find potential clues in order to identify the quarries used to obtain the materials.

Richard Hewitt (Universidad Complutense de Madrid)

STSM title: Integrating Geochemical and Geophysical data from archaeological sites in the R environment: Shared experiences and future directions

STSM start and end date: 2021-08-30 - 2021-09-17, Host: Czech University of Life Sciences

The purpose of the STSM was to build a research collaboration between two COST action member countries, Spain and Czech Republic, by linking research teams in each country through their SAGA COST action participants. The research collaboration will look to develop state-of-the art approaches to spatial-temporal data modelling and analysis of disparate archaeological data sets and sources, e.g. aerial photographs, historic maps, geophysical survey, archaeological find spot data. It will deliver three outcomes (deliverables); D1) a joint research agenda or memorandum of understanding specifying defining future collaboration around data integration in the form of research grant applications, R tools and code, student projects, fieldwork and scientific outputs etc (on completion of the STSM); D2) An R-based spatial model or analysis framework for the automated and integrated analysis of compositional data from geophysical and geochemical survey (up to 6 months after completion of the STSM); and D3) draft a scientific article for publication in an international impact factor journal with recommendations for the relevant fields (up to 1 year after completion of the STSM).

GRANT PERIOD 4

[Gaston Mendoza Veirana \(Ghent University\)](#)

STSM title: From lab to landscape: soil magnetic measurements as basis for strategizing and interpreting prospection data.

STSM start and end date: 01/04/2022 to 06/05/2022, Host: Institute of Geophysics of the Czech Academy of Sciences

The aim of short-term scientific mission, was to characterise common soils and sediments that are dominant in Flanders and the Netherlands. In addition, they target geophysical characterisation of a complex type of archaeology, related to Neolithic settlement in these regions, to provide a basis for landscape archaeological research that to date has remained impossible due to the absence of appropriate survey methods. Specific emphasis was given on characterising the magnetic properties of sampled soils, providing information on the genesis of geophysical responses, as well as providing prior information to support forward (and inverse) modelling procedures.

[Neli Jordanova \(Bulgarian Academy of Sciences\)](#)

STSM title: Magnetism of Neolithic structures – a focused look into possible causes of extremely high magnetic response.

STSM start and end date: 01/07/2022 to 12/07/2022, Host: Geophysics Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences Ludwig-Maximilians-University Munich

Magnetic prospection studies of Neolithic sites in Central and SE Europe, and laboratory mineral magnetic investigations on fired clay remains from the same epoch detect extremely high magnetisation values pertinent to this oldest period from the beginning of the agrarian-based human's evolution. Irrespective of the specific site's occupation history and location, very high concentration of strongly magnetic iron oxides, producing strong magnetic signal, is particularly characteristic to these sites. We were inspired by the fact that this oldest period of human's life organised in settlements, demonstrates one of the highest firing temperatures among those achieved in clay firing during the last ~ 8000 y. B.P. Our major aim was to explore possible reasons for the observed phenomena, involving multidisciplinary approach by combining magnetic prospection data and environmental magnetism. We planned a common work on summarising data compiled up to know by us, as well as other published data for the period concerned. Following systematic investigation and statistical analysis provided a basis for answering the research question posed.

[Sebastiano D'Amico \(Department of Geosciences, University of Malta\)](#)

STSM title: Study of anthropogenic water systems through the use of geophysics and soil science.

STSM start and end date: 09/07/2022 to 30/07/2022, Host: University of Palermo

The aim of this Short Term Scientific Mission (STSM) was to visit, map, and data collection (soil samples as well as geophysics and geomatic data) at several anthropogenic water systems located in the Northern part of Sicily. The systems are locally known as qanats and they represent an important historical and cultural value to the territory.

The main goal of the this STSM was targeted towards:

- Mapping of existing anthropogenic water systems in the Northern part of Sicily (mainly in Mt Nebrodi) and create a GIS database of those;
- Search of new ones based on ground evidence and geophysics data collection;
- Create a preliminary digital repository of the anthropogenic water systems by the means of photogrammetry and laser scanner applications;
- Collection of soil samples in order to extract information
- provide extra information about soil characteristics.
- assess the capability of targeted and minimally invasive soil sampling for soil geochemical analysis to locate the potential presence of pollutant

SUPPORTED STSMs (2021-2023)

Different Qanat systems, mapped, investigated and digitalised during the STSMs.

[Elina Aidona \(Aristotle University of Thessaloniki\)](#)

STSM title: Re-evaluation of magnetic properties of soils from Neolithic sites in Thessaly (Greece): comparison with geochemical data.

STSM start and end date: 18/07/2022 to 21/07/2022, Host: NTNU University Museum, Norway

The aim of this STSM was to discuss and gain insights from the findings of an unpublished test study in order to: a) Re-evaluate the magnetic susceptibility data obtained during this study and analyse complementary data of other magnetic properties (IRM, thermomagnetic curves), b) Combine these results with chemical analyses (phosphate) aiming to assess the capability of targeted and minimally invasive soil sampling and measurement to locate Neolithic sites, c) provide extra information about anomalies of interest (possible structures and ditches), detected after large area magnetometer surveys.

The targeted features that were the focus of this study are common elements in the few Thessalian Neolithic sites (Central Greece) that have been excavated. Their makeup, use or function are not completely understood from an archaeological perspective. Particular questions we wanted to address in this comparative study were: a) could the magnetic properties of soils act as alternatives for locating such targets if geophysical surveys were not possible? b) can we say anything else beyond the information about the geometry and spatial distribution of the possible buried features detected during the magnetometer surveys? c) if so, how feasible is to do this as part of large-area geophysical campaigns?

[Clare Wilson \(University of Stirling\)](#)

STSM title: Combining soil science and geophysical methods in exploring truncated Neolithic Magoules: soil chemistry perspective.

STSM start and end date: 18/07/2022 to 21/07/2022, Host: NTNU University Museum, Norway

The aim of this STSM was to discuss and gain insights from the findings of an unpublished test study of 3 truncated Neolithic Magoules (Rizomilos, Almyriotiki, and Perdika) with contrasting geology and morphology near Thessaly, Greece, in order to:

- assess the capability of targeted and minimally invasive soil sampling for soil geochemical analysis to locate and understand truncated Neolithic Magoules.
- provide extra information to help interpret and understand geophysical anomalies of interest (possible structures and ditches) detected after large area magnetometer surveys.

The STSM focussed on the integration of soil chemical information with magnetic susceptibility and geophysical survey data for maximum extraction of archaeological information.

SUPPORTED STSMs (2021-2023)

[Luciano Galone \(University of Malta\)](#)

STSM title: Geophysical investigation of an archaeological site in the Baix Penedès (Barcelona, Spain).

STSM start and end date: 05/09/2022 to 23/09/2022, Host: Universitat de Barcelona, Spain

This STSM aims to identify the optimal solution for field data collection by using complementary near-surface geophysics techniques in the prospection and identification of archaeological heritage in pre-excavation tasks at a site in the Baix Penedès.

This STSM has three specific objectives:

- 1) To employ a multi-scale approach where complementary geophysical methods are used at different work scales, which, in combination with other archaeological and geomorphological data and observations, generate an efficient workflow for the study case, which can be replicated at other unstudied sites in the area and other analogue study cases.
- 2) Facilitate excavation planning tasks for field archaeologists and students involved in the study area, generating anomaly maps that can be related to possible archaeological targets.
- 3) To provide practical training to the applicant in different techniques of near-surface geophysics applied to archaeological sites.

The study area has abundant Iberian remains that suggest kiln structures. The local archaeological team has determined the need to perform prospecting tasks to confirm or not the kiln's presence and to document them.

Ceramic remains found.

Left: Cleaning task. **Center:** Magnetic data acquisition. **Right:** Checking data on field.

[Jeroen Verhegge \(Ghent University\)](#)

STSM title: Identifying geophysical, physical and spectral soil properties of Brześć Kujawski culture traces in glacial soils of Kuyavia.

STSM start and end date: 10/09/2022 to 25/09/2022, Host: University of Warsaw

The Neolithic Brześć Kujawski culture originates to the Kujawy region but is present across the sandy Polish lowlands. It is characterised by monumental longhouses with a trapezoidal plan in relatively compact settlements. These sites are known from aerial photography and excavations, but are hardly detectable with fluxgate gradiometer survey. While the cause for this is unclear, the appearance of crop marks suggests the presence of moisture contrasts and therefore also probably electrical and/or dielectric permittivity contrasts, at least temporarily.

SUPPORTED STSMs (2021-2023)

The STSM was aimed at performing the survey and sampling fieldwork required to evaluate the physical soil properties and variables; determining potential magnetic susceptibility, electrical conductivity and/or dielectric permittivity contrasts between the longhouse features and the soil matrix, and enabled cross-temporal logging of soil variables by installing a monitoring station. Once established, these geophysical soil properties parametrised forward models, assist in developing site specific optimised survey approaches and contribute to general pedophysical models.

Similarly, the collected physical soil properties and variables were related to the cropmarks observed through remote sensing to investigate relationships between geophysical and spectral contrasts.

This helped us interpret the (lack of) detectable features in fluxgate gradiometer survey, electromagnetic induction survey and multispectral drone orthophotography.

Left: Excavation of test trench 1 at Radojewice. **Right:** Hydraprobe measurements on the profile of a house feature in trench 1 at Radojewice.

[Jakob Kainz \(University of Vienna\)](#)

STSM title: The assessment of geophysical methods for the monitoring of archaeological sites in the Province of Mantua, Italy.

STSM start and end date: 04/10/2022 to 20/10/2022, Host: Soprintendenza Archeologia, Belle Arti e Paesaggio for the provinces of Cremona Lodi and Mantova

The project is in cooperation with the Soprintendenza Archeologia, Belle Arti e Paesaggio for the provinces of Cremona Lodi and Mantova (the regional county archaeologist for the Province of Mantua) with the principle aim and motivation being the demonstration of the applicability of geophysical methods in the region. The planned work will help demonstrate the benefits of using non-invasive methods, such as multi-method geophysical surveys, for the investigation and management of buried archaeology. This is especially important considering the recent regional droughts and the traditional agricultural practices of deep ploughing carried out there. These circumstances have dramatically increased the threat to known and especially unknown buried archaeological remains in the region. It is therefore vital to promote the use of non-invasive methods for investigating and managing buried archaeology, as the current tools rely heavily on traditional and mainly invasive methods, like excavation and test pitting.

To evaluate the use of geophysics across the different geographic and archaeological settings in the Mantua region complementary geophysical surveys (magnetometry, GPR & EMI) was undertaken. Six sites located in different geographic and archaeological settings, dating from the Early Bronze Age to the 13th century AD, have been chosen to obtain data from a wide range of settings. To help explain the results and improve the interpretation of the geophysical data it will be necessary to identify and characterise the contrasts between the natural soil, the archaeological site soil and the archaeological features at the sites.

SUPPORTED STSMs (2021-2023)

[François-Xavier SIMON \(Inrap\)](#)

STSM title: Review of the low frequency electromagnetic method in archaeology: Potential, Pitfalls, and Perspectives.

STSM start and end date: 10/10/2022 to 14/10/2022, Host: Ghent University

Compared to other geophysical methods, frequency domain electromagnetic (FDEM) surveying is not widely used. There are several reasons that underly this reality. First, there are specific technical constraints that impede straightforward use of these devices (offset, calibration), alongside the need for stable data acquisition systems which minimise the influence of roll and pitch on obtained measurements. However, EM methods offer the possibility to investigate complex electrical and magnetic properties at different depths of investigation, and at different operating frequencies. Through the characterisation of the spatial distribution of electrical and magnetic properties, it is possible to go beyond a simple mapping of apparent geophysical properties. Inversion algorithms make it possible to proceed to a 3D or pseudo-3D characterisation of the mapped features and soils distribution. As a consequence of its potential, FDEM allows investigating the link between soil properties, their spatial distribution and their physical characteristics. This integral interpretative potential makes it highly valuable as part of geoarchaeological studies.

The aim of this STSM is to review the implementation of EM methods in archaeology. Recent advances have made it possible to consider EM devices as interesting devices for archaeological prospection and soil mapping. In some cases, they can be used as a substitute for electrical, magnetic or radar methods. Although they have a lower spatial discrimination potential, they can be used to investigate several geophysical properties simultaneously. From a technical vantage point, the targeted review will make a synthesis of existing methods for FDEM instrument calibration and drift correction, alongside an evaluation of forward modelling approaches. Next, an overview will be made of the main archaeological applications of FDEM; which kind of sites are most explored with FDEM, in which environments.

[Agnes Schneider \(Leiden University\)](#)

STSM title: How to tame Ambiguity: addressing Uncertainty on Data and Interpretation level by means of magnetic susceptibility measurements.

STSM start and end date: 25/10/2022 to 27/10/2022, Host: Geophysics Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences Ludwig-Maximilians-University Munich

The purpose of the STSM is to discuss with experts from the Landesamt für Denkmalpflege Bayern, especially with Prof. Dr. Jörg Fassbinder the results of the susceptibility measurements acquired during the first field work campaign in spring 2022 in al-Hira, Iraq, which is part of the international project "The Late Antique and Early Islamic Hira – Urbanistic Transformation Processes of a Trans-regional Contact Zone" funded by DFG. The susceptibility measurements are part of a PhD thesis which is a project component. The PhD aims to develop a reproducible workflow for the automated analysis for two large-scale magnetograms acquired of al-Hira. To understand the connection of anomalies in the magnetograms and the actual objects in the ground, magnetic susceptibility measurements have been conducted on the ground and in the two excavation trenches.

During the fieldwork the magnetic susceptibility mapping of the topsoil was adjusted to the circumstances, so that 4 approaches have been tested. The goal of the STSM is to evaluate all 4 approaches and work out which approach or the combination of approaches is best suited to be continued the next and last field season (February-March 2023) of the DFG project.

GRANT PERIOD 5

[Jakob Kainz \(University of Vienna\)](#)

STSM title: An assessment of the detectability of archaeological features in the province of Mantua, Italy.

STSM start and end date: 01/02/2023 to 28/02/2023, Host: Institute of Geophysics of the Czech Academy of Sciences

The overall project was coordinated by the Soprintendenza Archeologia, Belle Arti e Paesaggio for the provinces of Cremona, Lodi and Mantova. The main aim is to illustrate the applicability of geophysical methods for the management of archaeological sites in the Province of Mantua, Lombardy, Northern Italy. A previous grant helped undertaking the geophysical surveying and sample collection (CA17131 / E-COST-GRANT-CA17131-69c60c38). The carried-out work

SUPPORTED STSMs (2021-2023)

involved magnetometry and GPR surveys at various sites, which indicated a variability for features throughout the sites and region.

Examples of visible and invisible features are evident at the two sites of Casalromano and Asola Saccole, near Asola, Lombardy. At Casalromano aerial photographs indicate numerous archaeological features, however these are to the majority not visible in the magnetometry data, while the overall most features are visible in GPR data. One of the invisible features is a barrow ditch, which is clearly visible in the aerial photograph and in the GPR data, however completely invisible in the magnetometry data. At the site of Asola Saccole, however the ditches of four barrows are clearly visible in the magnetometer data and aerial photograph.

To verify the geophysical survey results trial trenches were opened at Casalromano, stretching across several linear and pit features as well as the northern part of the barrow ditch. A smaller trench over two pit features to the northeast of the barrow was also opened and reveal these to be two cremation burials. The excavation allowed the collection of samples from the various features within the trench while additional samples were collected by coring from features that were outside the excavation. This enabled collecting samples from a variety of features that were either visible or invisible in the magnetometer data and background samples from non-archaeological areas. For comparison samples were collected from one of the barrow ditches and a non-archaeological area at Asola Saccole.

Profile of the barrow ditch at Casalromano.

Profiles of the eastern cremation burial at Casalromano.

[Andrei Asandulesei \("Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University from Iasi\)](#)

STSM title: Review of the low frequency electromagnetic method in archaeology: Potential, Pitfalls, and Perspectives.

STSM start and end date: 27/02/2023 to 16/03/2023, Host: Geophysics Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences Ludwig-Maximilians-University Munich

The STSM had as its main objective the review of the field acquisition, the processing and interpretation for datasets collected using GPR and ERT techniques for some burial mounds belonging to Early Bronze Age from Romania, in order to better understand all these steps mandatory for integrated based archaeology projects. The main scientific question of this endeavour was related with the identification and correct interpretation of main or secondary graves from the burial mounds and any other additional specific features (e.g., ring ditches at the base, circular or rectangular enclosures located close to the mounds).

In order to gain improved knowledge necessary for data interpretation, the first part of my STSM was focused on the literature review regarding the methods in question and also concentrating on finding the analogies for similar archaeological situation. The Historicum building library from the LMU and the Bavarian state library were the two main places used for the documentation.

Further activities were related with magnetic data processing for the tumuli already together prospected in Romania (Bicaz archaeological site, NW Romania) using MagMap, MagPick and Geoplot version 4 software. Res2DInv and RES3DInv was used for ERT data processing for other mounds belonging to same chronological period, but located on the Eastern part of Romania. ReflexW and cloud-based Mala Vision software were used for the processing of GPR profiles. Aerial pictures for the main case study (Bicaz, Romania) were processed to obtain a DSM (digital surface model) to be subsequently integrated in a GIS project.

SAGA DATABASE

SAGA's database is now available to assist in the planning and conduct of primary research in archaeological prospection

The database is one of the main outputs of the shared and a community-based and community-achieved goals of the SAGA activities. It stores important information well usable by the whole community working in archaeological prospection and geophysics. The database is suited to serve well as a knowledge base, as well as a platform storing information usable for international research cooperation.

The database consists of the six main parts: "Equipment", "Sites", "Environmental Data Sources", "Methods", "Funding Sources", "Zotero SAGA Library" (Figure 1). The Equipment and Sites are planned to be used when a cooperation is sought: what type of equipment is available (to try, to borrow, to rent) in various institutions in the COST countries? What interesting sites in such countries could be used for research, workshop or training school? These are the questions our database can answer. Funding sources is the part also supporting international cooperation, as the information about the funding possibilities in some countries can be found here. Environmental data will be used probably mainly due to the specific research – both in progress or in preparation. This is a source containing the links to various national web sources (usually maps) presenting info about the geology, soils, hydrology and many more – very well usable in soil science, archaeology, geophysics and related disciplines. The parts of Methods and Zotero SAGA Library are mostly oriented on disciplinary knowledge base. While Methods being a general presentation of the methods used in archaeological prospection, The other is a link to a Zotero collection of publications and studies from this discipline.

Working with database

Figure 1.

The database is accessible via the SAGA website, from the main menu (<https://www.saga-cost.eu/>). After it is finished by the SAGA officially, it will be opened for the public use – to search and also to add new info.

Searching

Searching is done in every of those six parts (searches only in that respective part – Figure 2) via two ways, accessible after entering the part by clicking on its button: general full-text search, or filtering (by specification in one or more fields). Leaving a condition as "none" returns all entries. Both ways return a list of entries containing the searched string, or meeting the filter conditions. The list is opened in a new tab of a browser and can be also downloaded as a csv file (Figure3).

The screenshot shows the SAGA Database website. At the top left is the SAGA logo with the tagline 'The Soil Science & Archaeo-Geophysics Alliance'. To the right is a 'PANEL' button with a user icon. Below the logo is a navigation bar with links for 'SAGA', 'ACTIVITIES', 'DATABASE', 'OUTPUTS', and 'ABOUT COST'. The main heading is 'DATABASE - EQUIPMENTS'. Below this are three buttons: 'BACK TO DATABASE', 'ADD NEW EQUIPMENT', and 'MY EQUIPMENTS'. A search bar contains the text 'Search in Equipments ...' and a 'SEARCH' button. Below the search bar is a 'Filtered Search' section with four dropdown menus: 'Country' (set to 'Belgium (3)'), 'Method class' (set to 'none'), 'Hosting Institution' (empty), and 'Data acquisition' (set to 'none'). A 'SEARCH' button is located below these filters.

Figure 2.

Click on the button to download the results of your search

(31) Results for METHOD CLASS="none" and DATA ACQUISITION="none"

[Earth resistance survey](#)

Measurement of earth resistance with four-electrode array (including multiplexed) from the surface. For surveys the electrode array is moved over the area of investigation and earth resistance measured. The measured resistance (Ohm) can be converted to apparent resistivity as an estimator for the average resistivity of the soil. There are different ways of measurements such as electrical soundings, electrical profile or mapping and electrical resistivity tomography (ERT). Sounding are usually...

[Seismic Prospection \(Reflection, Refraction, Multi-Channel Analysis of Surface Waves\)](#)

The application of seismic methods to archaeological targets is very limited and it involves interpretive difficulties due to the very shallow depths of these objectives. Seismic methods include three different applications in archaeological areas: reflection, refraction and multi-channel surface waves.

[Self-Potential \(SP\)](#)

The self-potential (SP) method is very rarely used in archaeological prospection. Electrokinetic phenomena are the main generator of potential anomalies in archaeological areas. Also the electrochemical potentials are important to generated the electrical voltages in archaeology. The measured variable is the natural electrical potentials of the Earth from less than a millivolt to over one volt. SP changes are caused by the effects of electrical changes in the soil and they are due to the...

Figure 3.

SAGA DATABASE

Adding new information

Every part interface (except the Zotero Library) has an “add” button (Figure 2). There you can create a new entry and fill in the fields – there are informative descriptions to help – (Figure 4), or decide, if the entry should be publicly accessible (can be changed repeatedly). To change already existing entries, go through “My” entries (Figure 2, Figure 5). After new entry is added by SAGA non-member, the entry has to be approved by a SAGA member (the status can be seen in a list of My entries). The Zotero library part is just a link to a Zotero database (https://www.zotero.org/groups/2385112/cost_action_saga/library) with its own processes of a new entries additions.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Individuals: Gender-Balance

Individuals: ITC

Countries: inclusiveness

SAGA MEMBERS - EVOLUTION

Training School
"Magnetic laboratory methods in support of archaeo-geophysical research"
in Prague, Czech Republic

Trainees

Training School
"Training in ER and GPR survey with related geoarchaeological methods"
in Valandovo, N. Macedonia

Trainees

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